

Qualitative Analysis Of Superconductivity By Robin Singh

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Kamerlingh Onnes, in 1911, discovered a strange phenomenon while cooling mercury to extremely low temperatures. He observed that its internal resistance seemed to suddenly vanish as its temperature got close to 4.2K (or -268.95°C or -452.11°F). You can imagine how strange this must have been, in fact, it was so strange that many scientists proposed various theories and failed to explain this strange phenomenon for nearly a century!

The discovery of superconductivity can be traced back to at least the early 19th century and the discovery of the procedure to make liquid chlorine by Michael Faraday. Briefly explaining, one winter day, he took crystals of chlorine hydrate ($\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) and placed them in a sealed glass tube the upper end of which was hermetically closed. Then he heated the tube and noted the formation of a coloured oily liquid on subsequent cooling of the tube. On further analysis, he found out that this was liquid chlorine. But wait! We know today that we need to cool down chlorine to -34°C for it to become a liquid. Well, it turns out that the increase in pressure in the sealed tube when it was heated was enough to bring the boiling point or the liquefying point up to the room temperature of Faraday's lab.

After this followed a series of events that led to the development of methods to achieve very low temperatures which is a crucial development on the path which led to the discovery of superconductivity. This has been discussed in the later part of this paper.

1.2. Scope

Before we delve deeper into the mysteries of superconductivity, I think it is important to define the scope of this paper, and what it will and will not cover. Superconductivity is an advanced topic of solid-state physics and in order to understand the mathematics and quantitative aspects of the topic, deep knowledge of quantum mechanics, calculus, linear algebra, and tensor calculus (although vector calculus should also suffice but tensor calculus is recommended), basics of solid-state mechanics, etc. Due to these reasons, I will keep the main focus of this paper on providing a qualitative explanation of various phenomena and building up to superconductivity, involving equations only when it helps to understand the topic at hand. After we cover the basics, we shall also explore various applications of this amazing phenomenon both current and future. We will also discuss its newest findings and think about how they can be used to further improve the world.

2. Theoretical Background 1 (QUANTUM MECHANICS)

2.1. Wave functions and Quantum States

In order for us to understand superconductivity, it is essential to have some foundation in quantum mechanics. In fact, the most modern theory Bardeen-Cooper-Schrieffer or BCS theory, and the formation of cooper pairs cannot be explained by classical mechanics at all.

First of all, I need to explain what exactly is a “**state**”. It is simple business really, a set of physical quantities that describe the current ‘*situation*’ the particle is in, represent the **state** of that particle. For instance, let us consider a neutral particle going through empty space affected by no force with some velocity, the only things I need to describe the entire ‘*situation*’ of the particle are its momentum and mass, or its momentum and velocity, or its mass and velocity. Only 2 physical parameters are enough for us to know all that we can know about that particle. As I have shown, there may be multiple feasible ways or combinations of physical quantities to define the state of a certain particle or there may be only one feasible way, it depends on the situation.

Now that you know what a state is, let us consider what a **quantum state** is. This part is a bit awkward to introduce since I will need to just tell you about it without explaining it or deriving it mathematically (which is, as I have said earlier, not in the scope of this paper). According to the basic theory of quantum mechanics, we cannot *know* precisely, the state of any quantum particle or quanta, we can only know a part of its state. This is known as the general uncertainty principle and is mathematically derivable.

$$\sigma_A^2 \sigma_B^2 \geq \left(\frac{1}{2i} \langle [A, B] \rangle\right)^2 \text{(both A and B are operators)} \quad \dots (1)$$

Where σ_A is the standard deviation of A;
 $\langle [A, B] \rangle$ represents the expectation value
 (which is just a fancy way of saying “average value”);
 And, $[A, B] \equiv AB - BA$

(this value is often called the commutator and describes how well A and B fail to commute).

This equation is the **General Uncertainty Principle**. This is proved in [Appendix A](#) in detail if you are interested. You may notice the i in the denominator on the right side of the equation, this i cancels out with the i from $\langle [A, B] \rangle$ (the commutators’ expectation value). You have probably seen the **Heisenberg’s Uncertainty Principle**

$$\sigma_x^2 \sigma_p^2 \geq \left(\frac{1}{2i} \langle [x, p] \rangle\right)^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

Well, the $\langle [x, p] \rangle$ works out to be $i\hbar$, so

$$\sigma_x^2 \sigma_p^2 \geq \left(\frac{\hbar}{2}\right)^2 \quad \dots (3)$$

Since the standard deviations are positive by nature:

$$\sigma_x \sigma_p \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} \quad \dots (4)$$

This is not just because we have a hard time measuring these physical quantities (even though we do), it is something more fundamental than that. Some physical quantities can be measured simultaneously and some cannot. ¹Specifically, those that can commute with each other can be measured simultaneously (also known as *compatible observables*) and the ones that don’t commute cannot be measured simultaneously (also known as *incompatible observables*).

At this point you might ask ‘If we can’t know about the state of a particle, how then does quantum mechanics go about describing the particle?’, this leads us to our next topic of discussion, **wave functions**. According to the statistical interpretation, we can talk about the state of the particle by

considering the probability of that particle being in a specific state. This probabilistic interpretation of quantum mechanics troubled many scientists. This can be understood better if we take an example of a particle in empty space. We define a function that gives us the probability (more accurately probability amplitude as we will see in later sections) of that particle being in that specific position. That function is known as the *wave function*.

2.2. Schrödinger Equation

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t} = \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \Psi}{\partial t^2} + V\Psi \quad \dots (5)$$

The above equation is the Schrödinger Equation where Ψ (Greek letter ‘psi’) represents a complex function that is our wave function. I will not derive this as it will get quite complicated. There is a simpler derivation where we can derive this equation from classical mechanics but that is unnecessary and will only create misconceptions in the reader’s intuition. Strictly speaking, it is classical mechanics which should be derived from quantum mechanics, not the other way around. All you need to understand from this equation is that it is a differential relation which is really useful for calculating the wave function.

In order to solve this equation, we split it into 2 parts one purely time-dependent and one purely position-dependent.

$$\Psi(x, t) = \psi(x)\varphi(t) \quad \dots (6)$$

Some of you might object that this won’t give us all the solutions to the Schrödinger Equation and some will be excluded, but for practical purposes, they never occur in the real world so physicists tend to ignore them.

After some mathematical manipulation, $\psi(x)$ ’s relation comes out to be:

$$\frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2} + V\psi = E\psi \quad \dots (7)$$

It can also be written as:

$$\hat{H}\psi = E\psi \quad \dots (8)$$

Where \hat{H} is the Hamiltonian and is acting as a Hermitian operator. Here ψ is acting as an **Eigenfunction** and E is the **Eigenvalue** of this equation. It is important to note carefully that \hat{H} is an operator and E is a scalar, a simple number. The Hamiltonian operator acts or “operates” on the wave function and returns a scaled version of the wave function. On taking out the scalar quantity from the wave function, we get E , the energy of the system.

‘All right, but what is this good for?’ you might ask. The Schrödinger Equation is one of the most important equations in all of quantum mechanics. As an example, let us consider a simple case of the hydrogen atom. We want to know the wave function for the position of the single electron that ‘revolves’ around the nucleus. We can do that by solving the Schrödinger Equation for that specific case. The equation is usually solved in polar coordinates and gets quite lengthy.

Fig 1. Shows a plot of the probability of finding the electron at various points in space. Notice the 3 numbers in the bottom right corner of each graph, they represent quantum numbers that are used to define the state of the electron. They are ordered (n, l, m) where n is the principal quantum number, l is the Azimuthal Quantum number, and m is the magnetic quantum number. n represents the *energy* associated with the electron, both l and m are responsible for representing the angular momentum of the electron and they also determine the shape of the probability plot you just saw. Also, n and l only take on integer values and m can take on pseudo-integer values ($\pm 1, \pm 1.5, \pm 2 \dots$).

There are a few restrictions on the values of l and m quantum numbers as per the set value of the principal quantum number. I shall explain them briefly here. The azimuthal quantum number, l , is restricted to exist between 0 to $n-1$ (both included), and for every value of l , the magnetic quantum number, m , can exist from $-l$ to $+l$ (both included). These restrictions may seem random and you may be puzzled as to why this is the case, but when we go through the formalism of quantum mechanics, these seemingly unnecessary restrictions come out as natural results.

2.3. Quantum Tunneling

Quantum Tunneling is another phenomenon that is really important for superconductivity. It is something that only exists in quantum mechanics. Let us consider a situation classically then convert that situation and look at it from a quantum mechanics point of view.

Let us consider a ball rolling up and down a valley between 2 hills, but there is a further even

deeper valley across the mountain. When it is at the bottom-most point of the higher valley, all of its energy is in the form of kinetic energy. This kinetic energy is converted into potential energy as the ball moves up the mountain. Any sort of frictional loss is assumed to be negligible. In this case, in which the ball's energy is insufficient to cross the mountain, the ball will continue to oscillate back and forth forever.

In Fig 2. The ball can't gain energy from anywhere and use it to cross the hill and get to the deeper valley.

Now let us convert this problem into something that we can look at from a quantum mechanical point of view. The ball represents a particle and the valley represents a potential 'well'. The particle is stopped from getting to an even deeper potential well i.e. to lower its energy even further, by the potential 'wall' that is represented in the above situation by the hill.

Fig 3 X

In Fig 3, our particle is present in the region present between P and Q. The potential wall is represented by the region Q to R, and after R is a low potential 'valley'. The particle doesn't have enough energy to 'climb' the potential wall so, classically speaking, it should never be able to get to the lower potential region after R. But this is where quantum mechanics comes in. It turns out that when we compute the wave function, there is some probability of the particle ending up on the other side of the energy barrier! Interesting right? This phenomenon is known as **Quantum Tunneling**. Of course, this effect has its limitations too. Practically speaking this can only take place when the barrier is extremely thin and the particle in question is 'small'. Theoretically speaking, there is always some probability, regardless of the size of the particle, that quantum tunneling will occur (Though I wouldn't recommend running towards a wall hoping that quantum tunneling will save your nose from getting flattened), but the odds of such an event taking place is astronomically low (and yes, we can calculate the odds given the right information).

Also, don't misunderstand and think that this phenomenon can only be created in extremely controlled environments like a lab, it is something everyone has seen without knowing it! For a short example, take a beaker made of glass and place your dry hand on the outer surface of the beaker (the beaker must be dry from the outside), and try to see your fingers from the outside. You will probably not see anything (if you do see a little of your fingers, this means that the humidity in your area is high). Now pour some water on your hands to make them wet and repeat the above experiment. You will be able to see the part of your hand in contact with the beaker easily now. This is due to quantum tunneling (if you find this interesting, I encourage you to search for more details about it on the internet).

2.4. Pauli's exclusion principle

Well, now it is time to introduce you to the concept of 'spin' of quantum particles. This topic is really famous on the internet, but because of the large amount of misinformation or incomplete

information, it is widely misunderstood. The name “spin” is in itself a bit misleading; we don’t know that an electron is itself spinning, it is just that its magnetic properties can be explained if we assume the electron to be spinning in a direction corresponding to the magnetic field.

It is not a good practice to take this analogy any further than this. It is also important to note that, unlike the spin of any classical object, say a ball, which is just the sum of the total angular momentum of all the molecules that make up that ball with respect to the spin axis, the ‘spin’ in quantum mechanics is something more *intrinsic* than what can be classically derived. Also, the spin in the 3 coordinate axes does not commute. That is to say, it is fundamentally impossible to know, with absolute certainty, the S_x and S_y (or any other pair of x, y, and z) of an electron.

$$[S_x, S_y] = i\hbar S_z \quad \dots (9)$$

Where $[A, B] \equiv AB - BA$ (A and B are both operators)

In an atom, an electron’s spin is denoted by a 4th quantum number s . In general, this number can be an integer or a fraction like $\pm\frac{1}{2}, \pm 1, \pm 1\frac{1}{2}, \pm 2\dots$ and so on, and its range is the same as m but when talking about the electrons, we only need to concern ourselves with the $\pm\frac{1}{2}$ value of s and the integral values of m . This is because of the various boundary conditions placed on the electrons by the nucleus.

Paulie’s exclusion principle states that no *electron* bound to an atom will have all 4 quantum numbers the same. To exemplify, this means that no two electrons can have $n=2, l=1, m=1$, and $s=+\frac{1}{2}$. The closest they can get is one having configuration $n=2, l=1, m=1$, and $s=+\frac{1}{2}$, and the other having configuration $n=2, l=1, m=1$, and $s=-\frac{1}{2}$ (this is a specific case for atoms, its general case will be discussed roughly in the next topic).

2.5. Fermions and Bosons

All elementary particles are classified into **fermions** and **bosons**, based on their spin quantum number. **Fermions** are particles that have half-integer spins ($\pm\frac{1}{2}, \pm 1\frac{1}{2}\dots$), like the electron, proton and neutron. These follow the *Pauli’s exclusion principle* and no 2 fermions can have all 4 quantum states the same. On the contrary, **bosons** are particles that have integer spins ($\pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3\dots$) and don’t follow Pauli’s exclusion principle. Photons, Higgs-bosons, gluons and phonons. Also, Bosons can be created or destroyed singly, whereas fermions can only be destroyed in matter-antimatter pairs. As to why this is, there is no conceptual explanation that I know of that can easily explain Paulie’s principle. We can ‘derive’ it in *relativistic quantum mechanics* but in non-relativistic quantum mechanics, it is simply taken as an axiom².

Electrons only take on $+1/2$ or $-1/2$ and are classified as fermions and sure enough, they obey Paulie’s principle. This is an important fact upon which all particle physics and chemistry is based upon.

3. Theoretical Background 2 (SOLID STATE PHYSICS)

3.1. Crystal Structures

Solids are made up of atoms and molecules tightly bound to one another via molecular *bonding*. These solids are categorized based on the arrangement of atoms and molecules. If the arrangement of

molecules is periodic and neat, it is called a **crystalline solid** and if there is a seemingly random and messy arrangement of molecules, the solid is called an **amorphous solid**. Of course, there are those who can't be classified into just these 2 categories, and some are a mix of both.

We shall discuss crystals in detail to gain some qualitative intuition that will help us understand superconductivity. This gives rise to the question 'But why crystals, why not non-crystalline solids?'. Well, that is because the electronic properties of solids and their interaction with the ion nucleus are best understood by looking at crystals rather than non-crystals. Their regular arrangement makes it easier for us to see what is going on at the molecular level.

Before we study the interactions of electrons and ion centers, it is important to first familiarize ourselves with some basic concepts and terminologies.

"An **ideal crystal** is constructed by the infinite repetition of *identical groups*. A group is called the **basis**. The set of mathematical points to which the basis is attached is called the **lattice**.

$$\mathbf{r}' = \mathbf{r} + u_1\mathbf{a}_1 + u_2\mathbf{a}_2 + u_3\mathbf{a}_3$$

Here, u_1, u_2, u_3 are arbitrary integers. The set of points \mathbf{r}' defined by the above equation for all u_1, u_2, u_3 defines the lattice.

The lattice is said to be **primitive** if any 2 points from which the atomic arrangement looks the same satisfy the above equation with a suitable choice of the integers u_i " (this has been quoted from the textbook 'Introduction to Solid State Physics' by Charles Kittel)

The above text is important to understand as it forms the foundation of all solid-state physics. Every basis in a given crystal is identical to every other in composition, arrangement, and orientation.

A **primitive cell** is a parallelepiped defined by the **primitive axes** $\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \mathbf{a}_3$. A primitive cell is a minimum-volume cell and the basis corresponding to the primitive cell is called the primitive basis. No other basis has fewer atoms than the primitive basis. There is always one lattice point per primitive cell. If the lattice points lie at the corners of a primitive cell, then the total number of points in the cell is still one as $8 \cdot (1/8) = 1$.

There is a neat and sort of mechanical way of choosing a primitive basis called the **Wigner-Seitz cell**.

“The cell may be chosen by first picking a lattice point. After a point is chosen, lines are drawn to all nearby lattice points. At the midpoint of each line, another line is drawn normal to each of the first set of lines. The smallest area enclosed in this way is called the **Wigner–Seitz primitive cell**” (the above text and Fig 5 are taken from Wikipedia.com).

Fig 5

Now, we shall take a look at some fundamental types of lattices. Namely the simple cubic lattice (sc) Fig 6.1, the body-centered cubic lattice (bcc) Fig 6.2, and the face-centered cubic lattice (fcc) Fig 6.3. (courtesy of Wikipedia.com)

Fig 6.1

Fig 6.2

Fig 6.3

These images depict the 3 most important types of lattices in solid-state physics. Note that ‘a’ is the primitive axis in the case of sc but not in the case of bcc or fcc lattice; we have used ‘a’ to simply compare the three.

3.2. The Reciprocal Lattice and Brillouin Zones

We shall now discuss a concept that can prove to be a little hard to wrap your head around the reciprocal lattice. In short, **the reciprocal lattice** is the *Fourier transform* of the real lattice. Unfortunately, the mathematics can get a little complex, so we will just look at the derived expressions. Let’s first look at the relation that is derived between the reciprocal lattice vectors and the real lattice vectors.

$$b_1 = 2\pi \frac{a_2 \times a_3}{a_1 \cdot (a_2 \times a_3)}; \quad b_2 = 2\pi \frac{a_3 \times a_1}{a_1 \cdot (a_2 \times a_3)}; \quad b_3 = 2\pi \frac{a_1 \times a_2}{a_1 \cdot (a_2 \times a_3)} \quad \dots (10)$$

The factors of 2π are not necessary but are convenient in solid-state physics. One good way to visualize this relation is to imagine a cube in real space and tinker with it and calculate and observe how it changes the shape in the reciprocal lattice; by doing so we can see the naming sense of ‘reciprocal’ lattice.

Let us, for now, look at the reciprocal lattice as a normal everyday lattice and perform the process of drawing the Wigner–Seitz primitive cell in the reciprocal lattice. The area enclosed in the primitive

Wigner-Seitz cell is called the first **Brillouin Zone**. This has significant applications in solid-state physics. That's all well and good, but what is the significance of these concepts? Well, Brillouin Zones represent specific regions in a reciprocal lattice that define the allowed **wavevectors** (**k**-vector) for electrons in the crystal lattice. **Bloch's theorem** states that the wavefunctions of electrons in a crystal lattice can be written as a product of a periodic function and a plane wave. The **k**-vector specifies the electron's state within the Brillouin zone. We can analyze the connection between **k**-vectors and electronic properties. But what is most appreciable about this concept is that we only need to study the electron's behavior for one Brillouin zone as the **k**-vectors repeat (for a crystal lattice of course) further.

3.3. Basic Band Theory

This is the most important part of the theoretical background section, and it is the most interesting and relatively easy to understand as well (that is, according to me at least). To understand this concept easily, we will look at the state of the electronic configuration of a single isolated atom first, then a 2-atom system (in which the atoms are bonded together). And then we shall discuss the case most relevant to us, the crystal lattice.

A single, isolated atom is the easiest to discuss as we already know the shape of its electron cloud, as we have discussed in section 2.2 and even showed the electron cloud density plot-diagram for the hydrogen atom. Things begin to change, however, when we move on to 2 bonded atom structures. The orbitals of each individual atom are disturbed as they face electrical repulsion from the neighboring atom's electron cloud. However, since they are bonded together, this leads to extra complexity. It is important to realize that the 2 atoms are 'bonded together' is just another way of saying that they are sharing their electron cloud density with each other in order to expel excess energy and have as little energy as possible. Due to these effects, it isn't accurate to think of electrons as being present in 'atomic orbitals', but it is more accurate to think of them as forming 'molecular orbitals' (mo's), that is, orbitals for electrons of the molecule as a whole. This is known as the molecular orbital theory MOT and it is one of the best theories that has been successful at explaining the properties of various compounds.

This has many consequences and many other details like the role of bonding and anti-bonding mo's in the stability of the molecule and the number of unpaired electrons leading to various magnetic properties. But for now, we are only interested in the 'energy aspect' of mo's.

Now we shall look into the electrons in a crystal lattice. A crystal, in practice, is a very long array of atoms arranged in a similar manner. The electrons of each atom are brought so close together and there are so many orbitals that this causes overlapping between the orbitals leading to not a discrete spectra of energy levels or orbitals but an almost continuous 'band' of different energy levels. These are known as **energy bands**. There are gaps in the energies of these bands which are not allowed by the quantum mechanical model, these are known as **band gaps**. Loosely speaking, there are 2 types of energy bands; the **valence band** which is the band of energy levels that is filled up first at 0k following Pauli's principle; it is a derivative of the highest occupied atomic orbitals; then there is the **conduction band** which is just *above* (above, as in having more energy) the valence band and is empty at 0k, and the electrons can 'jump' to it when they are given energy. It is derived from the atomic orbitals just above the filled orbitals.

Having different band gaps between the valence and the conducting bands can greatly influence the properties of the said material.

If the band gap is non-existent i.e. the valence and conduction bands are overlapping or touching then the material is called a conductor, this is because the electrons can jump into the conduction band without much energy.

If the band gap is small, that is, in between 0.1 to 3.0 eV, then the electron can jump up to the conduction band with some energy. These materials are known as semiconductors. The electrons won't have this energy when sitting idle, but when given some external energy via sunlight or via applying potential difference, they are able to move to the conduction band. They have a lot of applications in the modern world, in fact, it wouldn't be an exaggeration to say that most of today's modern technologies rely on semiconductors.

If, however, the band gap is more than 3.0 eV, then the electrons need so much energy to move to the conduction band, that they are not able to conduct even when they are given a source of energy. These materials are used to protect electronics and used as insulation. They have a lot of applications in safety and other electronic components like capacitors, transformers, inductors, etc.

4. Fundamentals of Superconductivity

4.1. Main Properties

We shall now look at the various properties of superconductors.

First of all, we should know exactly what a superconductor is. When a certain metal is cooled down to a certain temperature, its electrical resistivity suddenly drops to zero or so close to zero that currents can continue to flow within these conductors without external potential difference. This is, however, only half of the story.

Along with the drop of internal resistance, the magnetic fields if present inside the conductor

are expelled. This phenomenon is really interesting as it leads to properties that enable the levitation of superconductors on magnets. This is a loose description of the **Meissner Effect**.

The temperature at which the ‘transition’ takes place between normal to superconductor is called the **critical temperature** (T_c). This T_c can vary with many other conditions like pressure.

But it is not all sunshine and rainbows. The effect of expelling the magnetic field can also ‘**break**’ the superconductivity if the magnetic field is strong enough. Unfortunately, this value isn’t much for pure metal superconductors like mercury. Many scientists of the time were frustrated by this. Fortunately, there have been immense developments in the field of superconductivity which has enabled us to create ‘high-temperature’ superconductors that can also withstand much stronger magnetic fields, which is necessary for them to be useful. The term high temperature is a relative term of course; even the highest-temperature superconductors are way below room temperature.

You may have heard the term ‘Type 1’ or ‘Type 2’ superconductors before, I shall explain briefly what is the difference between them. Type 1 superconductors are a more traditional type of superconductor, they have a fixed line where they transition from a normal conductor to a superconductor. They have a low tolerance to magnetic fields and break easily.

Fig 8.1

In Fig 8.1, we can see how a type 1 superconductor behaves in an applied magnetic field. The range of magnetic fields in which the superconducting state persists is relatively small.

Fig 8.2 depicts a type 2 superconductor. The material remains in a pure superconductive state for a lesser value of magnetic field but then enters a semi-superconductive state called the **vortex state**. In this state, the magnetic fields are sort of threaded in the material. This vortex state is also responsible for the

Fig 8.2

levitation of superconductors on magnets.

Fig 9 shows the Meissner effect on a type 1 superconductor as it is cooled. The material sort of forms a

binary system, where either it is superconducting or not; either it is repelling the magnetic field or letting it pass through.

Fig 10 shows the transitions of a type 2 superconductor, where it goes from a normal conductor (letting all the magnetic fields pass through), to a vortex state superconductor (letting the magnetic field pass through from a few spots), and then finally to a pure superconducting state. Also, as a side note, the term ‘vortex’ was chosen to describe this phenomenon as this occurs due to the formation of a stable current vortex inside the superconductor.

Note: It can be seen from the above graphs that even if the temperature is absolute zero, the superconductivity can still be broken if the magnetic field is strong enough.

4.2. Qualitative Analysis of BCS Theory and London Equations

Fig 11.1

Fig 11.2

Ever since superconductivity was discovered, there have been many attempts at formulating a theory that can explain this phenomenon. The most successful theory to date is the **Bardeen-Cooper-Schrieffer (BCS) theory**. This theory was formulated by John Bardeen, Leon Cooper, and Robert Schieffer in the year 1957. Now it acts as a foundation that helps us develop the field of superconductivity and apply it to solve problems in the real world. It explains the formation of **Cooper pairs**, and how they lead to the formation of a superconducting state.

It is common knowledge that the electrons in a normal metal repel each other and, when subjected to an external electric field, travel in the direction opposite to that of conventional current, all while bumping into each other and the kernels (+ve ion core). Their drift velocity is around the order of 1mm/s (or 10^{-3} m/s) but the actual speed at which they travel is of the order of 10^6 m/s. All this wastage of energy is avoided in superconductors because of the formation of cooper pairs.

Let's consider an electron traveling in a straight line, passing between the positive kernels (see Fig 11.1). As the electron travels, it attracts the positive kernels and creates a sort of temporary positive charge in the area it just left. The kernels relax back to their normal positions as the electron moves forward.

During that time there is a window where if an electron comes from behind, the attraction by the kernels is more than the repulsion by the first electron at that distance, which leads to lower energy. This leads to the formation of a pair of electrons stuck together due to a stable configuration.

This pair of electrons travels straight without bumping into any obstacle. This pair of electrons is called the **Cooper pair** (see Fig 11.2). These Cooper pairs can only be formed at low temperatures when the electrons and the kernels don't vibrate as much. These pairs have a lower energy state than individual electrons which leads to the formation of an energy gap. They are also the reason for some of the macroscopic properties of superconductors. The energy gap of the Cooper pairs is also the energy required to break the pair. The higher the value of this band gap is, the more stable the cooper pair formation and the better the superconductor. Mathematically, the band gap is represented by delta and is a function of temperature.

$$\Delta(T) = \Delta(0) \left[1 - \left(\frac{T}{T_c} \right)^4 \right]^{1/2} \quad \dots (11)$$

This gap increases as the temperature is lowered and becomes zero at the critical temperature (T_c). The Cooper pairs move without electrical resistance as the energy gap prevents the electrons from scattering.

The BCS theory can explain the electromagnetic response in superconductors. The Cooper pairs condense into a coherent quantum state that can be described by a macroscopic wavefunction. The density of superconducting electrons is given by the square of that wave function.

Fig 12

The **London Equations** were developed by brothers Fritz and Heinz London in 1935. They describe the electromagnetic properties of superconductors. The key equations are:

$$\nabla \times J_s = \frac{-1}{\lambda_L} B ; \nabla \cdot J_s = 0 \quad \dots (12)$$

Where J_s is the current density, B is the magnetic field, and λ_L is the **Penetration Depth**. The penetration depth describes how deep inside the surface of the superconductor, the magnetic field can penetrate. Typically, this depth is not much and is negligible unless the superconductor is extremely thin.

In Fig 12, a type 1 superconductor has been placed in an external magnetic field. The magnetic field penetrates the

surface of the superconductor and decays exponentially inside the material. The penetration depth λ_L is really small, around the order of 10^{-8} m. In the diagram, λ_L has been exaggerated for ease of viewing.

4.3. Basic Ginzburg-Landau Theory

The Ginzburg-Landau theory, named after Vitaly Ginzburg and Lev Landau, is a theory used to explain the macroscopic aspects of superconductivity. It can explain the YBCO (very famous superconductor) and all cuprates.

GL theory represents the density of Cooper pairs and their phase in terms of a complex order parameter field $\psi(\mathbf{r}) = |\psi(\mathbf{r})|e^{i\theta(\mathbf{r})}$. The magnitude of $\psi(\mathbf{r})$ is related to the local density of Cooper pairs, and its *phase* is related to the quantum mechanical phase of the superconducting wavefunction. GN theory relates this with the free energy density:

$$f_s = f_n + \alpha|\psi(\mathbf{r})|^2 + \frac{1}{2}\beta|\psi(\mathbf{r})|^4 + \frac{1}{2m^*}(-i\hbar\nabla - \frac{e^*}{c}\mathbf{A})\psi(\mathbf{r})|^2 + \frac{B^2}{8\pi}, \quad \dots (13)$$

Where,

f_n is the free energy density of the normal phase.

α and β are phenomenological parameters and are a function of 'T'.

m^* is the effective mass of the Cooper pair.

$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{A} \times \nabla$ is the Magnetic field.

\mathbf{A} is the magnetic vector potential.

e^* is the effective charge of the Cooper Pair.

The 2 GL equations are:

$$1) \quad \nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \frac{4\pi}{c}\mathbf{J} ; \mathbf{J} = \frac{e^*}{m^*} \text{Re} \left\{ \psi^* (-i\hbar\nabla - \frac{e^*}{c}\mathbf{A})\psi \right\} \quad \dots (14)$$

$$2) \quad \alpha\psi + \beta|\psi|^2\psi + \frac{1}{2m^*}(-i\hbar\nabla - \frac{e^*}{c}\mathbf{A})^2\psi = 0 \quad \dots (15)$$

These equations describe the behavior of the superconducting order parameter and the current density \mathbf{J} in the presence of an electromagnetic field.

The GL theory also introduces 2 fundamental lengths: the **Coherence length** and the **Penetration depth**. We already know penetration depth from the previous section, as for the coherence length, it characterizes spatial variation of the order parameter.

In GL theory, the electrons in a material in the superconducting phase form a **Superfluid**. In this interpretation, $|\psi|^2$ indicates the proportion of electrons that have condensed into a superfluid.

4.4. Some Effects of Tunneling of Superconductive Electrons

The tunneling of particles under suitable conditions has been discussed in section 2.3 of this paper. This effect has amazing applications in superconductivity. Under suitable conditions, we observe tunneling of Cooper pairs through a layer of insulator into another superconductor. This junction is called a *weak link*. The effects of this phenomenon include:

DC Josephson effect (DC is for direct current): A direct current flows across the junction in the absence of any electric or magnetic fields

AC Josephson effect (AC stands for alternate current): a DC voltage applied across the

junction causes the current to oscillate across the junction with a frequency in the range of around 3 kHz to 300 GHz, which corresponds to the frequency of radio waves (often called RF current). This effect has been employed in determining a precise value of \hbar/e . Further, if a voltage with a frequency in the RF range (commonly known as RF voltage) is applied with the DC voltage, can cause a direct current flow across the junction.

Macroscopic long-range quantum interference: A DC magnetic field applied through a superconducting circuit containing two junctions causes the maximum supercurrent to show interference effects as a function of magnetic field intensity. This effect can be utilized in sensitive magnetometers.

(These results can be derived mathematically, relatively easily).

5. Experimental Methods

I don't wish to turn this paper into a purely theoretical one, so, I have included some experimental methods of how to practically measure various properties of superconductors.

5.1. Measuring the electrical resistance

Measuring the resistance of a superconductor is quite straightforward.

- First, we need a power supply that can supply us with a constant current with variable voltage.
- Then, we can connect our superconducting material sample and measure how much voltage is required to pass the set amount of current (see Fig. 13).
- When the sample is in a normal phase we will get a finite amount of voltage on our voltmeter.
- When the sample is cooled down to its critical temperature, the voltage across the sample suddenly drops to zero.
- We can use the simple equation $R = V / I$ in classical Ohm's law to depict that the resistance has truly reached zero.
- Of course, the instruments used have to be extremely precise, and the resistance of the connecting wires must be taken into account and calibrated accordingly.

This technique is called the four-point measurement technique.

5.2. Critical Magnetic Field Determination

When the magnetic field reaches a certain value, the superconductivity breaks down. It is extremely

important to keep this phenomenon in check, whenever dealing with superconductors. This also enables us to measure the properties of the material below the critical temperature that, otherwise would have been affected by superconductivity.

- To measure the critical field, we can follow a simple procedure.
- First, we set up the apparatus for the 4-point-measurement technique.
- Then, we cool down the sample till the superconducting state is achieved.
- Then, constantly looking at the reading, we slowly turn on the magnetic field and proceed to increase it while keeping the temperature of the superconductor constant.
- During incrementing the magnetic field, at some point, the superconductivity will vanish even while maintaining the critical temperature.
- This value of this magnetic field is called the critical magnetic field.

6. Applications of Superconductivity

Whenever we study a topic, we must look at its applications.

Firstly, the most important application of superconductors is the ability to form strong electromagnets with no wastage of energy. The following are some applications of the magnetic effect of superconductivity:

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI): You have most probably heard of the word MRI before. It refers to a test to see the insides of your body through very strong magnetic pulses. The frequency of these pulses is very sophisticated to get the best result. It is mostly used to ‘look’ inside a person’s head. The name MRI is actually derived from NMR which stands for ‘Nuclear Magnetic Resonance’ (it is quite clear that doctors had to make this change to not scare people away). MRI usually focuses on the nucleus of the hydrogen atom, because our tissues (especially our brain) have a lot of water, thus a lot of hydrogen atoms. The magnets in these machines need to be at least a couple of teslas (our earth’s magnetic field is roughly 0.00005 tesla), so normal electro-magnets waste a lot of energy as heat, but superconductors can do this job easily and quite efficiently (the only inconvenience is that we have to cool the superconductor).

Magnetic Levitation Trains (Maglev): Trains that rely on electromagnets for levitation, rather than conventional wheels. This requires extremely strong electromagnets to lift the train, and creating such magnets via conventional methods would waste so much energy that all the gain of efficiency gained by frictionless travel would be eclipsed by this loss. Hence, the use of electromagnetics made of superconductors is essential.

Particle Accelerators: Particle accelerators are used in particle colliders like the large hadron collider in the USA to study elementary particles and discover their properties. This works by accelerating the particles to relativistic speeds (near light speeds), by using strong electromagnets. These electromagnets also require a lot of power and current to run. This has been solved by superconductors. To demonstrate just how efficient superconductors are, see Fig-14.

Electric cables for accelerators at the **European Organization for Nuclear Research**. Both the massive and slim cables are rated for 12,500 A. Top: regular cables for LEP; bottom: superconductor-based cables for the LHC

Quantum Supercomputers: The CPUs and GPUs in our conventional servers can draw dozens of amps and get heated quickly. To solve this, we employ coolers which in turn waste more energy. But this sort of inefficiency is a fatal problem for supercomputers. So, we use superconductors to minimize the amount of heat generated (I say minimize as the transistors and other components made of semiconductors will unavoidably generate heat, so some heat will still be produced).

7. Current Challenges in Superconductivity

The study of superconductivity is a relatively new and unexplored one. There is no shortage of things in superconductivity that are covered in mystery.

One example of this is **High-Temperature Superconductivity (HTS)**. To begin with, materials that have been observed to show HTS cannot be fully explained by the BCS theory, this demonstrates the point that we are far from being done with the development of theoretical models explaining superconductivity.

Discovering materials that exhibit HTS is a challenging task. Though many families of superconductors have been discovered that have much higher transition temperatures, the conditions they require to get to a superconducting state are non-practical. For example, the highest temperature superconductor currently known is LaH_{10} and its critical temperature is -27°C but it requires 170 GigaPascals pressure (for reference, $1\text{atm} = 0.1\text{ Gpa}$). See Fig 17

Fig 17 shows the discovery of various superconductors and the conditions for them to achieve superconducting state.

Another problem to consider is, that even if a room-temperature superconductor at atmospheric pressure was discovered, taking it from a lab sample to production at a large scale at a reasonable price range is, in itself, a challenge to be reckoned with.

8. What the Future Holds

While it is true that no man can predict the future, I *believe* with almost *absolute certainty*, that we will discover ways to make room-temperature superconductors and make them viable commercially. I have here some applications of superconductors at room temperature.

The first use that comes to mind is **commercially available supercomputers**, we can fit supercomputers into regular laptops and desktops if they don't require too much cooling. This will revolutionize the tech industry in almost every way. As more people gain access to enormous amounts of processing power, more people can work on developing stuff to improve our lives.

Another use of superconductivity might be in space travel and exploration. Energy efficiency is a major problem in satellites and rockets. What's more, is that it is really hard to gain any heat energy in space (that is if the object isn't exposed to the sun). So, we just have to cool our material down once and after that, we just need to maintain the pressure required for the transition.

Superconductivity can even be used to stabilize the orbits of old satellites by *flux pinning*, which would also enable us to re-vitalize the satellite with fuel and other supplies. If we manage to develop this kind of technology quickly, we may even be able to extend the lives of many of our satellites, even the International Space Station. If humanity gets to the level of having asteroid mining or perhaps even a Dyson sphere, no doubt, superconductors will be a big help.

Appendix A

Proof of General Uncertainty Principle: (Courtesy of Introduction To Quantum Mechanics By D. J. Griffiths)

For any observable **A**, we have:

$$\sigma_A^2 = \langle (\hat{A} - \langle A \rangle)\Psi | (\hat{A} - \langle A \rangle)\Psi \rangle = \langle f | f \rangle$$

Where, $f \equiv (\hat{A} - \langle A \rangle)\Psi$

And similarly, for an observable **B**:

$$\sigma_B^2 = \langle g | g \rangle, \text{ where } g \equiv (\hat{B} - \langle B \rangle)\Psi$$

Now, by using Schwarz Inequality,

$$\sigma_A^2 \sigma_B^2 = \langle f | f \rangle \langle g | g \rangle \geq |\langle f | g \rangle|^2$$

And for any complex number z ,

$$|z|^2 = [\text{Re}(z)]^2 + [\text{Im}(z)]^2 \geq [\text{Im}(z)]^2 = \left[\frac{1}{2i}(z - z^*)\right]^2$$

Therefore, letting $z = \langle f | g \rangle$:

$$\sigma_A^2 \sigma_B^2 \geq \left(\frac{1}{2i}[\langle f | g \rangle - \langle g | f \rangle]\right)^2$$

By utilizing the hermiticity of $(\hat{A} - \langle A \rangle)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle f | g \rangle &= \langle (\hat{A} - \langle A \rangle)\Psi | (\hat{B} - \langle B \rangle)\Psi \rangle = \langle \Psi | (\hat{A} - \langle A \rangle)(\hat{B} - \langle B \rangle)\Psi \rangle \\ &= \langle \Psi | (\hat{A}\hat{B} - \hat{A}\langle B \rangle - \hat{B}\langle A \rangle + \langle A \rangle\langle B \rangle)\Psi \rangle \\ &= \langle \Psi | \hat{A}\hat{B}\Psi \rangle - \langle B \rangle \langle \Psi | \hat{A}\Psi \rangle - \langle A \rangle \langle \Psi | \hat{B}\Psi \rangle + \langle A \rangle \langle B \rangle \langle \Psi | \Psi \rangle \\ &= \langle \hat{A}\hat{B} \rangle - \langle B \rangle \langle A \rangle - \langle A \rangle \langle B \rangle + \langle A \rangle \langle B \rangle \\ &= \langle \hat{A}\hat{B} \rangle - \langle A \rangle \langle B \rangle \end{aligned}$$

Similarly

$$\langle g | f \rangle = \langle \hat{B}\hat{A} \rangle - \langle A \rangle \langle B \rangle$$

So,

$$\langle f | g \rangle - \langle g | f \rangle = \langle \hat{A}\hat{B} \rangle - \langle \hat{B}\hat{A} \rangle = \langle [\hat{A}, \hat{B}] \rangle;$$

Where $[A, B] \equiv \hat{A}\hat{B} - \hat{B}\hat{A}$ is the commutator for \hat{A} and \hat{B}

Hence,

$$\sigma_A^2 \sigma_B^2 \geq \left(\frac{1}{2i} \langle [\hat{A}, \hat{B}] \rangle\right)^2 \text{ Q.E.D.}$$

This is the *Generalized Uncertainty Principle*.

Works Cited

Books

Griffiths, David J. Introduction to Quantum Mechanics. 3rd ed., Cambridge University Press, 2018

Kittel, Charles. Introduction to Solid State Physics. 8th ed., Wiley, 2004.

Blundell, Stephen. Superconductivity a Very Short Introduction. Oxford University Press, 2009

Articles and Papers

Anderson, P. W. "Theory of Dirty Superconductors." Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids, vol. 11, no. 1-2, 1959, pp. 26-30. Available at [ScienceDirect](#)

Bardeen, J., Cooper, L. N., and Schrieffer, R. "Theory of Superconductivity." Physical Review, vol. 108, no. 5, 1957, pp. 1175-1204. Available at [APS](#).

Ginzburg, V. L., and Landau, L. D. "On the Theory of Superconductivity." Zhurnal Eksperimental'noi i Teoreticheskoi Fiziki, vol. 20, 1950, pp. 1064-1082. Translated in Men of Physics: L. D. Landau, Pergamon Press, 1965. Available at [Internet Archive](#).

Leggett, Anthony J. "What Do We Know about High Tc?" Nature Physics, vol. 2, 2006, pp. 134-136. Available at [Nature](#).

Websites

MIT OpenCourseWare. "Solid State Physics (8.231)." Spring 2017, Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Available at [MIT OCW](#).

MIT OpenCourseWare. "Quantum Physics II (8.05)." Fall 2013, Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Available at [MIT OCW](#).

Figures

PoorLeno, "Hydrogen density plots for n up to 4. Wavefunctions of the electron in a hydrogen atom at different energy levels", 17 August 2008, Wikipedia. Available at [Wikipedia](#).

[Rama](#). "Regular and superconducting cables for 12,500 amperes used at LEP (top) and Large Hadron Collider (bottom) respectively. "Microcosme" exposition at the CERN.", 25 February 2006, Wikipedia. Available at [Wikipedia](#).

[PJRay](#). "Overview of superconducting critical temperatures for a variety of superconducting materials since the first discovery in 1911.", 19 November 2015, Wikipedia. Available at [Wikipedia](#).

Nölleke, Christian. "Construction of a Wigner–Seitz primitive cell.", 14 January 2007, Wikipedia. Available at [Wikipedia](#).

Stannered. "Simple cubic crystal structure.". 2 March 2007, Wikipedia. Available at [Wikipedia](#).

Stannered. "The body-centered cubic crystal structure.". 2 March 2007, Wikipedia. Available at [Wikipedia](#).

Stannered. "Face-centered cubic crystal structure". 2 March 2007, Wikipedia. Available at [Wikipedia](#).

Bouquet, Frederic and Bobroff, Julien. "Phase diagram (B, T) of a type I superconductor". 7 December 2011, Wikipedia. Available at [Wikipedia](#).

Bouquet, Frederic and Bobroff, Julien. "Phase diagram (B, T) of a type II superconductor". December 2011, Wikipedia. Available at [Wikipedia](#).